

Study protocol

Clinical Reasoning Curriculum in the Health Professions Education: A Scoping Review

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Background

Clinical reasoning is at the core of any health professions' clinical practice, accordingly it is a key component in higher education (Young et al., 2020). Clinical reasoning is defined as the thinking and decision-making processes that guides the actions of practitioners (Higgs & Jones, 2008). In practice, the clinical reasoning implies gathering and interpreting information, generating hypotheses and diagnoses as well as deciding on a treatment and evaluation plan (Edwards, Jones, Carr, Braunack-Mayer, & Jensen, 2004; Levett-Jones et al., 2010). Despite clinical reasoning being a core competence, research have demonstrated that it is scarcely taught or assessed explicitly, and clinical reasoning curricula guidelines would be beneficial (Harendza, Krenz, Klinge, Wendt, & Janneck, 2017; Kononowicz et al., 2020; Kuiper, 2013). A scoping review would highlight the link between clinical reasoning methods, teaching strategies and curriculum design, and provide guidance for faculty and educators in health professions education development.

Aim and objectives:

The aim of this scoping review is to advance clinical reasoning curriculum design through identification of how significant aspects of clinical reasoning have been integrated in health professions education.

The objectives are to explore:

- features of clinical reasoning curriculum design
- which theories, models or frameworks of clinical reasoning that have been used and how these have informed clinical reasoning curricula.
- which teaching content, methods and assessment forms that have been used and how these have informed the clinical reasoning curriculum design.

Methods

Design

Given a broad conceptualization and the pioneer phase of the knowledge area, a scoping methodology of literature review is selected. A scoping review is recommended when the field of interest is complex and has not been comprehensively reviewed (Arksey & O'Malley,

2005). The systematic methodological steps outlined in the Arksey and O'Malley (2005) framework and further enhanced by Levac et al (2010) will be used to conduct the study. The six-stage framework consists of: 1) Identifying the research question; 2) Identifying relevant studies; 3) Study selection; 4) Charting the data; 5) Collating, summarizing, and reporting the results; and 6) Consultation.

Literature search

Eligibility criteria

To be included in this scoping review the articles need to meet the following inclusion criteria: Peer-reviewed journal articles, including reviews and guidelines, published the latest 10 years; English language; describes a curriculum framework on clinical reasoning or aspects of such framework; describes and sets a) important aspects, b) a method or an example of clinical reasoning into a curricular perspective; and contribute with knowledge or examples that are valuable in the development of a clinical reasoning curriculum framework. The following exclusion criteria will be used: deals with clinical reasoning aspects or teaching methods without a connection to the curriculum or does not align with the greater picture of an education programme or deals only with a specific organ (e.g. kidneys) without putting it into a larger perspective.

Information sources and search strategy

To identify relevant studies, a search string has been developed and applied in the databases PubMed, Web of Science and Cinahl. The first search was performed in April 2020 and will be updated in the fall 2020. The search strings are presented in the appendix. In addition to database searches, manual searches in data bases and reference lists of included articles will be conducted.

Study selection

One author will conduct the database searches. All authors will contribute to identify additional articles. Covidence systematic review software (Veritas Health Innovation, Melbourne, Australia) will be used for the screening procedure. All eligible studies' titles and abstracts will be screened by two authors. In case of disagreement about study eligibility a third author will screen the title and abstract. Each full-text article will be assessed by three authors and the decision about inclusion will be made in agreement.

Charting the data

A data charting form will be developed to record the key information of the articles, such as author, reference, and results relevant to the aim and objectives of the scoping review. The charting will be performed iteratively, and the charting form will be further refined in early phases of the data charting. A draft of the data-charting form will be tested independently by two reviewers with about five articles, which will result in suggestions of improvement. The data charting work will be divided between the authors who will extract data independently. Uncertainty will be resolved by a second author or in team discussion. Correctness of data, presented in tables, will be checked by all authors.

Data synthesis

The data extracted from the included studies will be descriptively presented in a tabular form. A thematic analysis will be used as an analytic approach. The themes will be developed in team discussions. A narrative summary of the results will accompany the tabulated charted results and will describe how the results relate to the review aim and objectives.

Reporting

The PRISMA-ScR checklist (Tricco et al., 2018) will be used to structure and report the results.

Conflicts of interest

In case participant authors' articles are analysed, non-authors will be charting and perform primary analyses of these.

APPENDIX

Search strings and number of hits per database

All searches were limited to latest 10 years and peer-reviewed journal articles in English.

PubMed

April 28 2020: 774 hits

(Clinical reasoning[Ti] OR Problem solving[Ti] OR reasoning[Ti] OR decision making[Ti] OR judgment[Ti] OR judgement[Ti] OR narrative reasoning[Ti] OR diagnostic[Ti] OR clinical thinking[Ti] OR Management[Ti] OR Cognitive bias[Ti] OR medical error[Ti] OR Clinical competence[Ti] OR Heuristics[Ti]) AND (curriculum[TIAB] OR syllabus[TIAB]) AND (Journal Article[ptyp] AND "last 10 years"[PDat])

Web of Science

April 28 2020: 751 hits

(TI=(Clinical reasoning OR Problem solving OR reasoning OR decision making OR judgment OR judgement OR narrative reasoning OR diagnostic OR clinical thinking OR Patient Management OR Cognitive bias OR medical error OR Clinical competence OR Heuristics) AND TS=(Curriculum OR Syllabus) NOT TS= mathematic*) AND LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article)

Cinahl

April 28 2020: 385 hits

TI (Clinical reasoning OR Problem solving OR reasoning OR decision making OR judgment OR judgement OR narrative reasoning OR diagnostic OR clinical thinking OR Management OR Cognitive bias OR medical error OR Clinical competence OR Heuristics) AND AB (curriculum OR syllabus)

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